

Proposed prototype processes for the GAIA Global Iterative Solution

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9 March 2001

GAIA-LL-34 (v. 2)¹

ABSTRACT. A set of processes for large-scale experiments with the GAIA Global Iterative Solution is described. Three main processes determine (1) the astrometric parameters and mean magnitudes for each star; (2) the continuous telescope attitude; (3) geometric and photometric calibration parameters for each CCD on a time scale of a few days; and (4) one global parameter (the PPN parameter γ). Fortran code for many of the critical algorithms is provided.

1 Introduction

In the GAIA Study Report (ESA-SCI(2000)4, Sect. 9.5) the processing of astrometric data for GAIA is described in terms of a ‘Global Iterative Solution’ (GIS). This was the proposed way to deal with the complex task to simultaneously determine an extremely large number of stellar, instrument and attitude parameters. However, the feasibility of this scheme on a large scale, such as required for GAIA, has not been demonstrated. One of the critical aspects concerns the intricate ways in which extremely large bodies of data must be accessed, viz. essentially objectwise for the astrometric processing, and timewise for the attitude determination and instrument calibrations. While the scheme is obviously well suited for massive parallel computing (many astronomical objects or many time intervals could be processed independently at specific phases of the GIS), the proper sequencing and management of the processes is non-trivial.

It is believed that a database system could supply the required overhead structure for these tasks. In order to study the complexities of the GAIA data analysis and the feasibility of the proposed database approach, large-scale numerical experiments are being set up as part of the GAIA Data Access and Analysis Study carried out by GMV (Madrid) under ESA contract. The purpose of the present document is to specify the (slightly simplified) processes that could be used in these experiments to model the real GAIA data analysis.

In its original form, the GIS only concerned the astrometric/geometric part of the data analysis. However it is clear that a similar approach should be feasible for the photometric processing, which should therefore be considered in parallel with the astrometric processing and geometric calibrations. For more complex astronomical objects than single stars, it is

¹The original version was dated 24 January 2001. The present version is much expanded and revised.

even essential that all the photometric and astrometric information is considered jointly in the modelling. Nevertheless, this document deals mostly with the astrometric part, the photometric processing being, by comparison, fairly simple. For the moment, the radial-velocity observations are not considered, although the radial velocity is included as the sixth astrometric parameter in the astrometric modelling.

2 Scope of the large-scale experiments

The large-scale experiments should incorporate a range of representative processes, in particular those that can only be realistically tested on a global scale, e.g. dealing with the sky partitioning and data access patterns required by the real mission. The experiments must for instance be set up within the appropriate database structure.

On the other hand it is unnecessary, at the present stage, to burden the simulations with a multitude of details that are not critical for the practical or theoretical feasibility of the GIS or database approach. This does not mean that such details are uninteresting, merely that they are perhaps better studied in a different context, e.g. through dedicated simulations.

It is assumed that the experiments could deal with of the order of 1 to 10 million objects and the full mission length of 5 yr. This means that the ‘core processing’ (attitude and instrument calibration using a subset of well-behaved stars) can be simulated quite realistically, without the need for scaling. If simulations were constrained to a much smaller star density, then it would for instance be necessary to increase the size of the fields of view or CCDs in order to test basic principles, with a corresponding uncertainty in the interpretation of the results.

Given that we thus have the possibility to make tests on a global scale, we should concentrate on issues that are critical on a global scale. These (called type A below) are, for example,

- sky partitioning;
- data storage and access;
- interface with other tasks (e.g. those of type B and C), including modularity;
- practical and mathematical feasibility of the GIS scheme;
- geometric and photometric calibration, including chromaticity;
- robustness of the calibrations, e.g., what fraction of ‘problem stars’ — double, variable, etc. — can be tolerated?
- error propagation from individual transits (centroiding/flux error) to the astrometric/photometric parameters — have we missed something in the theoretical accuracy analysis?

On the other hand, the following issues (of type B) are examples of ‘local’ problems that could be studied decoupled from the above:

- image centroiding and flux measurement;
- details of CCD behaviour (CTI, etc.);
- analysis of individual ‘non-trivial’ objects — double and multiple stars, variables, etc.

There are some issues (of type C) that fall between the previous categories: they are mostly of a local nature, but involves some global aspects. They could benefit from using (part of) the ‘global’ software, but it would be overkill to incorporate them in full-scale simulations:

- object detection — the global aspect here is what happens in the different transits of the same object;
- object matching: full density (to 20 mag) is required, but only in small areas; all scans throughout the mission must be simulated, but most of the complications like attitude and calibration errors can be turned off; sky partitioning/data access issues come in but not for the whole sky, etc.;
- minor planets: cross identification and orbit determination;
- spacecraft dynamics — needs long temporal sequences but without relation to sky coverage, etc.;
- relativistic formulation: the global aspect only comes in if we want to study e.g. the determination of γ — otherwise (for fixed theory = GR) there is no need to complicate simulations by including relativity.

A reasonable strategy would then be to design the system around a skeleton of the tasks of type A, bearing in mind that some of type C perhaps also need to be included, although not necessarily from start. Forget about type B altogether; they could for the present purpose be represented by random-number generators.

Following this approach, four main processes are described and proposed to be incorporated in the data analysis experiments. In order to focus on the relevant *global* aspects, the processes are of course highly simplified. However, they are still quite realistic in the sense that they can be used e.g. to assess the global error propagation and stability of the solution.

3 Terminology

The processing is described in terms of the following entities:

SOURCE: The basic astronomical entity is called a *source*,² which in the present context means a small patch of the sky (of the order of one arcsec) which we want to characterize in terms of astrometric and photometric parameters. In reality this entity could be very complex, but for the present study only the simplest possible case is considered, viz. a single, constant star. This is completely characterized by six astrometric parameters and one magnitude per filter band (up to some 15 magnitudes in total, although not all need to be included in the prototype processing). The sources are here identified by index i .

ATTITUDE INTERVAL: The time evolution of the instrument pointing is described in *attitude intervals* of several hours. Within such an interval the attitude components (e.g. in the quaternion formalism of SAG-LL-30) are represented by cubic splines (Sect. 5.3). The length of such an interval could be 12 h. Each attitude interval is modelled independently of the others, i.e., continuity constraints at interval divisions are neglected. Both the interval divisions and knot sequences need to be dynamically changeable in the real data processing, but could be fixed for the present purpose. The attitude intervals are identified by index j .

CALIBRATION UNIT: In the real data processing the geometric and photometric characteristics of the instruments are described by the two angular coordinates and magnitude zeropoint of each CCD column. (Photometric non-linearity terms are probably also needed.) These could be slowly variable in time. The simplification proposed here is to regard the whole CCD as an independent entity for a certain time interval of a few days; this CCD \times (time interval) is called a *calibration unit* and identified by index k .³ Here we assume four parameters per calibration unit: the along-scan instrument angle η_k , an along-scan chromaticity factor Γ_k , a correction $\Delta\zeta_k$ to the nominal across-scan coordinate, and a magnitude zero point μ_k . See SAG-LL-30 for the definition of η , ζ . The zero point μ is the magnitude that generates an image charge (spot energy) of 1 electron.

ELEMENTARY OBSERVATION: The *elementary observation* (l) is the result of reading out a single patch from a single CCD. For the present study the individual sample values need not be considered: it is assumed that they have been processed to give three quantities, \tilde{t}_l , $\tilde{\zeta}_l$ and \tilde{m}_l (where the tilde indicates that they are observed values), and their standard errors. The first quantity is the time coordinate when the source image was at the along-scan coordinate $\eta_{k(l)}$ of the relevant CCD. The second is the across-scan coordinate of the image: in the present sampling scheme this is only obtained from the skymappers. The third is a magnitude in the instrument system, $m = 10^{-0.4a}$, where a is the image charge (spot energy) in electrons.

²This term was chosen instead of *object* in order to avoid confusion with established terminology within the Object Oriented framework of data processing.

³The time interval should be at least several times the satellite spin period, say 12 hour minimum, for the geometrical calibration to work *in principle*. A longer interval may in practice be necessary in order to have a sufficient number (tens of thousands?) of elementary observations per calibration unit. For instance, with a total of 10^6 stars available for the core processing, each CCD in the Astro fields makes about 4000 observations per day.

GLOBAL PARAMETERS: The GIS admits the inclusion of an (almost) arbitrary number of *global parameters*. The criterion for a global parameter is that any elementary observation (i.e., of any object and at any time) is in principle affected by it. For the sake of this study it is proposed to include just one such parameter, viz. the PPN parameter γ . By definition, no indexing is required for the globals.

There is a unique mapping from the elementary observations l to the other indices, such that $i(l)$ is the source observed in observation l , $j(l)$ is the corresponding attitude interval and $k(l)$ the calibration unit relevant for the observation. Subsets of the various indices can also be defined, as in

$$\left. \begin{aligned} L_i &= \{l : i(l) = i\} \\ L_j &= \{l : j(l) = j\} \\ L_k &= \{l : k(l) = k\} \\ J_i &= \{j : \exists l \text{ for which } i(l) = i \text{ and } j(l) = j\} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

etc. Part of the reason for having a database is the need to access these subsets efficiently.

4 Main processes

The main processes are:

1. SOURCE PROCESSING: estimate the astrometric and photometric parameters \mathbf{ast}_i for a given source i ;
2. ATTITUDE PROCESSING: estimate the parameters \mathbf{att}_j for the continuous attitude in a given interval j ;
3. CALIBRATION: estimate the geometric and photometric parameters \mathbf{cal}_k for a given calibration unit k .
4. GLOBAL PROCESSING: estimate the global parameters \mathbf{glb} .

For logistic reasons it may well be advantageous to do many of these processes in parallel, e.g. all the sources in a certain area of the sky, or all the calibration units. However the description below does not take this into account, and the system should of course allow a single entity to be processed when required.

The GIS can be described as the following sequence:

- (A) initialization of source, attitude, calibration and global data;
- (B) iteration of processes 2, 3, 1, 4 (or some other suitable permutation of the processes) for all the entities until convergence;
- (C) end of GIS — current data are the final results.

4.1 SOURCE PROCESSING

In principle the only input argument for this process is the source identifier i . The output is a flag telling whether the process was successful. The SOURCE PROCESSING performs the following tasks:

- 1.1 retrieve the current astrometric and photometric catalogue data for the source (**ast** _{i});
- 1.2 retrieve all the elementary observations of the source (**obs** _{l} for $l \in L_i$);
- 1.3 retrieve attitude data for the time intervals in which the source was observed (**att** _{j} for $j \in J_i$);
- 1.4 retrieve calibration data for the units in which the source was observed (**cal** _{k} for $k \in K_i$);
- 1.5 retrieve the global parameters **glb**;
- 1.6 update the catalogue data for the source (**ast** _{i}). This can be divided in two parts:
 - 1.6.1 astrometric updating, which is a robust least-squares processing of the geometric data (\tilde{t}_l and $\tilde{\zeta}_l$, see Sect. 5.5);
 - 1.6.2 photometric processing, which is simply a robust averaging of $m_l + \mu_{k(l)}$ (see Sect. 5.1);
- 1.7 from the goodness-of-fit statistics $P(\chi^2, \nu)$ of the catalogue updating, determine the success of the process and exit.

4.2 ATTITUDE PROCESSING

Assuming a predefined list of attitude intervals and knot sequences, the only input argument for this process is the interval index j . The output is a flag indicating whether the process was a success (or the quality of the attitude fit). The ATTITUDE PROCESSING performs the following tasks:

- 2.1 retrieve attitude data (**att** _{j}) for the interval;
- 2.2 retrieve all the elementary observations in the interval (**obs** _{l} for $l \in L_j$);
- 2.3 retrieve the current astrometric and photometric catalogue data for the sources observed in the interval (**ast** _{i} for $i \in I_j$);
- 2.4 retrieve calibration data for all the units in the interval (**cal** _{k} for $k \in K_j$);
- 2.5 retrieve the global parameters **glb**;
- 2.6 update the attitude parameters in **att** _{j} . This is done by robust least-squares fitting of the basic spline coefficients to the observations (Sect. 5.6);
- 2.7 determine the quality of the attitude, e.g. mean precision along and normal to scan, and exit.

4.3 CALIBRATION

The input argument is the calibration unit index k (or range of indices) and the output is a flag indicating whether the process was a success (or the quality of the calibration). The CALIBRATION performs the following tasks:

- 3.1 retrieve current calibration data for the unit (\mathbf{cal}_k);
- 3.2 retrieve all the elementary observations in the unit (\mathbf{obs}_l for $l \in L_k$);
- 3.3 retrieve the current astrometric and photometric catalogue data for the stars observed in the unit (\mathbf{ast}_i for $i \in I_k$);
- 3.4 retrieve attitude data for the relevant intervals (\mathbf{att}_j for $j \in J_k$);
- 3.5 retrieve the global parameters \mathbf{glb} ;
- 3.6 update the calibration data (\mathbf{cal}_k). The updates are basically just the robust averages of the astrometric and photometric residuals (or linear regression if chromaticity is included), see Sect. 5.7;
- 3.7 determine the quality of the calibration, e.g. mean astrometric and photometric precision, and exit.

Note: The astrometric and photometric residuals required for the calibration could be computed and stored (by index k) during the previous star or attitude process (whichever comes immediately before the calibration). In that case steps 3.2–3.4 are eliminated and 3.5 simplified.

4.4 GLOBAL PROCESSING

No input argument is needed. The GLOBAL PROCESSING performs the following tasks:

- 4.1 retrieve the global parameters \mathbf{glb} ;
- 4.2 retrieve all the elementary observations (\mathbf{obs}_l);
- 4.3 retrieve the associated astrometric and photometric catalogue data ($\mathbf{ast}_{i(l)}$);
- 4.4 retrieve the associated attitude data ($\mathbf{att}_{j(l)}$);
- 4.5 retrieve the associated calibration data ($\mathbf{cal}_{k(l)}$);
- 4.6 update the global parameters. The updates are obtained by a robust least-squares fitting to the observational residuals (Sect. 5.8);
- 4.7 determine the quality of the global parameters (standard errors and correlations), and exit.

5 Details of the modelling and some basic algorithms

In this section the proposed models and algorithms for some specific tasks are described in some detail, including Fortran listings (as indicated in the margin) of critical items. The purpose is to define in very concrete terms the proposed level of realism and complexity in the GIS simulations, and also to provide a starting point for the actual coding.

Fortran
routines

The header comments of the Fortran routines referred to in this section are listed alphabetically in the Appendix. The complete code (including dependencies) are available as the text files `LL34.f`, `const_math.h` and `const_astr.h`.

5.1 Robustness

All processing must be very robust. This is a property that must already be built into the basic algorithms. To combine the efficiency of least-squares processing with the requirement for robustness, it is proposed to minimize a non-euclidean norm such as the Huber metric⁴

$$\rho(z) = z^2 \times \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |z| \leq c \\ c(2c|z| - c)z^{-2} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where z is the residual normalized by the standard error of the observation and $c \simeq 2$ is the scale at which the downweighting, given by the second factor in the equation, starts to become effective. If the residuals are gaussian with unit standard deviation, then the average downweighting factor is 0.99857.

As an example, the Appendix contains a Fortran subroutine to compute a robust weighted mean of n real values, using the Huber metric. This could be used for the photometric updating (Sect. 4.1, item 1.6.2) and calibration (Sect. 4.3, item 3.6).

robwm

The weight modification has been implemented in the attitude updating algorithm (`attupd`, Sect. 5.6). It should be noted that least-squares solutions using this metric are non-linear, and have to be iterated until the updates are negligible.

Given that the individual algorithms are robust and that the GIS process itself is (hopefully) stable, the overall processing should also be robust. This can be tested by using simulated input with a certain percentage of ‘bad’ data, including double and variable stars. The system is robust if the attitude and calibration parameters, as well as the astrometric and photometric parameters for the ‘good’ stars, are correctly estimated. This comparison should take into account that the astrometric reference system has six degrees of freedom and each filter band has one degree of freedom, all of which are arbitrarily fixed by the GIS.

⁴Other metric choices may be better than this one, which is provided as an example.

5.2 Astrometric modelling

This section covers the calculation of the observable celestial direction to a single star, i.e. the proper direction \mathbf{u} . This is a unit vector ($|\mathbf{u}| = 1$) numerically represented by its components u_l, u_m, u_n along the principal axes of the celestial (equatorial) reference system.

Input for the calculation of proper direction \mathbf{u} is the global parameter γ (in `glb`), the astrometric parameters of the source (in `ast`), and the time t (which is the coordinate time in the chosen barycentric reference system). `dir_prp`

For a single star there are six *astrometric parameters*, viz.: $\alpha, \delta, \pi, \mu_{\alpha^*}, \mu_{\delta}$, and $\mu_r = v_R \pi / A$ (see ESA SP-1200, Vol. 1, Sect. 1.2.8).⁵ These refer to a pre-defined reference epoch T . For the arbitrary epoch $t = T + \tau$ the proper direction (normal to the incident wavefront in the co-moving frame of the observer) is obtained by a sequence of transformations. First the coordinate direction is computed by⁶

$$\bar{\mathbf{u}} = \left\langle \mathbf{r} + (\mathbf{p}\mu_{\alpha^*} + \mathbf{q}\mu_{\delta} + \mathbf{r}\mu_r)\tau - \mathbf{b}\pi/A \right\rangle, \quad (3)$$

where $[\mathbf{p} \ \mathbf{q} \ \mathbf{r}]$ is the normal triad at (α, δ) , \mathbf{b} the barycentric coordinate of the satellite, and A the astronomical unit. Next, gravitational deflection by the sun is included by transforming to the natural direction

$$\hat{\mathbf{u}} = \left\langle \bar{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{h} \frac{(1 + \gamma)GS c^{-2}}{h(h + \bar{\mathbf{u}}'\mathbf{h})} \right\rangle. \quad (4)$$

Here, \mathbf{h} is the heliocentric coordinate of the satellite, γ the PPN parameter, GS the heliocentric gravitational constant, and c the speed of light. Finally, the proper direction is obtained by a Lorentz transformation, yielding

$$\mathbf{u} = \left\langle \hat{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{v} \frac{1 + \hat{\mathbf{u}}'\mathbf{v}(c + e)^{-1}}{e} \right\rangle, \quad (5)$$

in which \mathbf{v} is the barycentric velocity of the satellite and $e = (c^2 - |\mathbf{v}|^2)^{1/2}$. The prime denotes scalar product and angular brackets denote vector normalisation.

In order to perform these transformations, it is necessary to have a barycentric ephemeris of the satellite and of the sun, from which \mathbf{b} , \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{h} can be obtained for arbitrary t . The subroutine `bary_sat` (called by `dir_prp`) returns these vectors computed from a simple analytical ephemeris good to $< 10^{-3}$ AU and $< 10^{-5}$ AU day⁻¹, in which the motion of the satellite relative to L2 is neglected. `bary_sat`

⁵In SP-1200 the sixth parameter was called ζ . Since that letter is here used for the across-scan instrument angle, I propose instead the designation μ_r , which could be loosely interpreted as ‘proper motion in the radial direction’ — it is expressed in the same unit as μ_{α^*} and μ_{δ} . It gives a neat look to Eq. (3).

⁶Actually the τ in Eq. (3) should not refer to the time of observation but to the corresponding barycentric epoch (which may differ by up to ± 500 s). In the real GAIA processing this is significant, but for the present model it is an example of the ‘higher-order effects’ that may be neglected.

5.3 Attitude modelling

At any time, the celestial orientation of the GAIA instrument axes is specified by the quaternion $\mathbf{q}(t)$. This is a 4-vector of unit length, i.e. $\mathbf{q}(t) = [q_1(t) \ q_2(t) \ q_3(t) \ q_4(t)]'$ with $q_1^2 + q_2^2 + q_3^2 + q_4^2 = 1$ for any t .⁷ Both the nominal attitude (see GAIA-LL-35) and the on-ground reconstructed attitude, and perhaps also the real-time attitude, can be represented by means of cubic splines followed by normalization (to ensure unit length). Thus, in the attitude interval $[t_{\text{beg}}, t_{\text{end}}]$ we have four cubic spline functions $s_m(t)$, $m = 1 \dots 4$ forming the 4-vector $\mathbf{s}(t)$, from which $\mathbf{q}(t) = \mathbf{s}(t)|\mathbf{s}(t)|^{-1}$. Although splines are well-known and widely used, they can be represented in a variety of ways, and I will therefore describe in some detail the proposed formalism, on which the attached routines are based.

Each of the functions $s_m(t)$ is a cubic spline defined on $[t_{\text{beg}}, t_{\text{end}}]$; it is therefore continuous in this interval and its first two derivatives $\dot{s}_m(t)$, $\ddot{s}_m(t)$ are also (usually)⁸ continuous. The third derivative is discontinuous at discrete points, called the knots, and constant between the knots. The frequency of knots determines the flexibility of the spline: more knots gives a more flexible spline. It is estimated that about one knot per 15 s is needed to adequately represent the attitude of GAIA. The same knot sequence is used for all four components of $\mathbf{s}(t)$.

A cubic spline can be represented in a number of different ways, e.g. by means of its value and second derivative at each knot (see Press et al., *Numerical Recipes*, Cambridge 1992). However, the method proposed here is to write the spline as a linear combination of non-negative local basis functions, called B-splines (see C. de Boor, *A Practical Guide to Splines*, Springer 1978). Let $B_n(t)$ ($n = 1 \dots N$) be the N B-splines defined on the attitude interval. Because the B-splines are linearly independent basis functions, N is also the number of degrees of freedom of the spline. Then

$$s_m(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N S_{mn} B_n(t), \quad m = 1 \dots 4 \quad (6)$$

and

$$\dot{s}_m(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N S_{mn} \dot{B}_n(t), \quad m = 1 \dots 4. \quad (7)$$

The B-splines B_n (and their derivatives \dot{B}_n) are uniquely defined by the knot sequence

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \{\tau_{-1}, \tau_0, \tau_1, \tau_2 \equiv t_{\text{beg}}, \tau_3, \dots, \tau_{N-2}, \tau_{N-1} \equiv t_{\text{end}}, \tau_N, \tau_{N+1}, \tau_{N+2}\} \quad (8)$$

and can be evaluated for any t according to a simple and stable recurrence relation. The knot sequence must be non-decreasing ($\tau_n \leq \tau_{n+1}$, $n = -1 \dots N+2$). For continuity of $s_m(t)$ it is also necessary that $\tau_n < \tau_{n+3}$ ($n = 0 \dots N+1$). At a given point $t \in [\tau_n, \tau_{n+1}]$ the only non-zero B-splines are B_{n-1} , B_n , B_{n+1} and B_{n+2} . The non-zero B-splines on the

⁷In SAG-LL-30 provision was made for a non-unit length formalism, but that is now found to be unnecessary. Thus it can always be assumed that $|\mathbf{q}| = 1$.

⁸The first derivative could be allowed to be discontinuous at specific instants, e.g. in order to accommodate significant rate changes caused by micrometeoroid impacts, but that possibility is neglected in the present model. Such discontinuities are allowed by inserting triple knots at the required instants.

whole attitude interval $[\tau_2, \tau_{N-1}]$ are, therefore, B_1, B_2, \dots, B_N . The additional knots on either side of the attitude interval are needed to define B_1, B_2, B_3 and B_{N-2}, B_{N-1}, B_N , and can be chosen arbitrarily as long as τ is non-decreasing.

For the present experiments it is probably sufficient to use equidistant knot sequences. This means that the attitude interval $[t_{\text{beg}}, t_{\text{end}}]$ is divided into $N - 3$ equal knot intervals, by insertion of $N - 4$ interior knots; to which are added eight more knots at the endpoints of the interval and exterior to it. For a given maximum knot interval $\Delta\tau_{\text{max}}$ ($= 15$ s, say), `taudef` a suitable sequence can be computed as follows:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} N &= \left\lceil \frac{t_{\text{end}} - t_{\text{beg}}}{\Delta\tau_{\text{max}}} \right\rceil + 3 \\ \Delta\tau &= (t_{\text{end}} - t_{\text{beg}})/(N - 3) \\ \tau_n &= t_{\text{beg}} + (n - 2)\Delta\tau, \quad n = -1 \dots N + 2 \end{aligned} \right\}. \quad (9)$$

The complete representation of the attitude interval is

$$\mathbf{att}_j \equiv \left\{ N, \boldsymbol{\tau}, \left\{ \{S_{mn}\}_{m=1}^4 \}_{n=1}^N \right\} \right\} \quad (10)$$

consisting of $5(N + 1)$ numbers. A 12 hour attitude interval with a mean knot separation of 15 s is thus specified by 14,420 numbers. Given these data and an arbitrary $t \in [t_{\text{beg}}, t_{\text{end}}]$ `qint` one can thus calculate \mathbf{s} and by normalisation obtain \mathbf{q} . From Eq. (7) we also have $\dot{\mathbf{s}}$, from which $\dot{\mathbf{q}} = [\dot{\mathbf{s}} - \mathbf{q}(\mathbf{q}'\dot{\mathbf{s}})]|\mathbf{s}|^{-1}$. (The time derivative of the quaternion is used to compute the instantaneous scan rates in the fields of view, important for the real-time operation, but not needed for the present analysis.)

5.4 Instrument angles

A very basic part of the processing is the theoretical calculation of the instrument angles $\mathbf{f}_l = [\eta_l \zeta_l]'$ for a given elementary observation l (at the observed transit time \tilde{t}_l), given the current data in `asti`, `attj`, and `glb`. We take the view that these angles should strictly correspond to the celestial directions expressed in the instrument frame, and are therefore independent of instrument calibration data. This can formally be written as

$$\mathbf{f}_l^{(\text{calc})} = \mathbf{f}(\tilde{t}_l, \mathbf{ast}_{i(l)}, \mathbf{att}_{j(l)}, \mathbf{glb}). \quad (11)$$

The first part of the function \mathbf{f} above is calculated by `dir_prp` as outlined above. Given the proper direction to the source $\mathbf{u} = [u_l \ u_m \ u_n]'$ and the attitude \mathbf{q} , the theoretical `dir_f` instrument angles (η, ζ) are computed from (SAG-LL-30)

$$\begin{bmatrix} \cos \zeta \cos \eta \\ \cos \zeta \sin \eta \\ \sin \zeta \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}) \begin{bmatrix} u_l \\ u_m \\ u_n \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

where

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{q}) = \begin{bmatrix} q_1^2 - q_2^2 - q_3^2 + q_4^2 & 2(q_1q_2 + q_3q_4) & 2(q_1q_3 - q_2q_4) \\ 2(q_1q_2 - q_3q_4) & -q_1^2 + q_2^2 - q_3^2 + q_4^2 & 2(q_2q_3 + q_1q_4) \\ 2(q_1q_3 + q_2q_4) & 2(q_2q_3 - q_1q_4) & -q_1^2 - q_2^2 + q_3^2 + q_4^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

Comparing the theoretical instrument angles with their observational counterparts results in observation equations for updating of the astrometric, attitude, calibration and global parameters. The observed quantities are actually the CCD transit time \tilde{t}_l for the along-scan coordinate, and the pixel column number (or similar) for the across-scan coordinate. The former is used in Eq. (11) to compute the theoretical along-scan angle, which must then be compared with calibration data. For the across-scan coordinate, we assume that the pixel column or similar is transformed to a continuous angle-like quantity which we designate $\tilde{\zeta}_l$. In analogy with the along-scan situation, we then apply the calibration datum $\Delta\zeta_k$ to get the quantity to be compared with $\mathbf{f}^{(\text{calc})}$:

$$\mathbf{f}_l^{(\text{obs})} = \begin{bmatrix} \eta_{k(l)} + \Gamma_{k(l)}(C_{i(l)} - C_0) \\ \tilde{\zeta}_l + \Delta\zeta_{k(l)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

where C_i is the colour index of the source and C_0 a reference colour index.

5.5 Astrometric updating

In the GIS, the astrometric parameters (\mathbf{a}) of the source are updated from a solution of the weighted least-squares equations. The linearised equations for the astrometric updates $\Delta\mathbf{a}$ are

$$\begin{bmatrix} (\eta^{(\text{obs})} - \eta^{(\text{calc})}) \cos \zeta^{(\text{calc})} \\ \zeta^{(\text{obs})} - \zeta^{(\text{calc})} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{a}'} \Delta\mathbf{a} + \text{noise}, \quad (15)$$

where $\partial \mathbf{f} / \partial \mathbf{a}'$ is the 2×6 matrix of partial derivatives returned by `dir.f`. Collecting all the observation equations for a specific source allows to set up and solve the normal equations for $\Delta\mathbf{a}$. The astrometric updating thus requires robust (iterative) solution of a system of equations with six unknowns.

Some *ad hoc* procedure is required to handle the sixth astrometric parameter μ_r . This can be determined astrometrically only for rather few stars, for which the perspective acceleration is measurable. Thus, for most stars it would result in a nearly singular system of normal equations. To avoid this, one could add an observation equation to each source corresponding to the *a priori* radial-velocity knowledge, which could be taken as simply $\mu_r = 0$ with standard error $\pi\sigma_{v_R}/A$, for $\sigma_{v_R} \sim 30 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. In the real processing, the actually measured radial velocity and its uncertainty should of course be used instead.

5.6 Attitude updating

We assume that the knot sequence $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ for a given attitude interval is fixed throughout the GIS, so that the successive iterations simply update the same set of B-spline coefficients S_{mn} . The knot sequence could be set up with `taudf` (see Sect. 5.3).

Since the observations depend on \mathbf{q} in a strongly non-linear way, it is necessary to have a good starting approximation for the spline coefficients. This could be obtained by fitting the coefficients directly to a set of real-time attitude vectors $\mathbf{q}(t_i)$. At least a few points per knot interval are needed. If the real-time attitude is not simulated, the nominal attitude vectors could be used for the same purpose. The fitting routine `splfit` takes into account that the normal equations matrix is very sparse: only a band of seven diagonals along the main diagonal contains non-zero elements. Furthermore, the matrix is symmetric, so that the relevant elements can be stored in a matrix of size $4 \times N$. The LINPACK subroutine `dpbfa` is used to factor the matrix, whereupon S_{mn} are obtained for $m = 1 \dots 4$ by calling `dpbs1` four times with different right-hand sides.

Subsequent updatings use the residuals in the instrument angles in analogy with Eq. (15):

$$\begin{bmatrix} (\eta^{(\text{obs})} - \eta^{(\text{calc})}) \cos \zeta^{(\text{calc})} \\ \zeta^{(\text{obs})} - \zeta^{(\text{calc})} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{q}'} \Delta \mathbf{q} + \text{noise}, \quad (16)$$

where $\partial \mathbf{f} / \partial \mathbf{q}'$ is the 2×4 matrix of partial derivatives returned by `dir_f`. However, it is not the \mathbf{q} (or \mathbf{s}) vector directly that should be updated, but the B-spline coefficients S_{mn} . If t is in the knot interval $[\tau_n, \tau_{n+1}]$ then $s_m(t)$ depends on $S_{m,n-1}$, $S_{m,n}$, $S_{m,n+1}$ and $S_{m,n+2}$ according to Eq. (6). The observation equation for the time t therefore involves 16 B-spline coefficients. The symmetric normal equations matrix is again banded along the diagonal, but now with up to 15 non-zero elements above (and below) the main diagonal. The same LINPACK subroutines `dpbfa` and `dpbs1` can be used to solve the resulting system of equations for the updates ΔS_{mn} .

The routine `attupd` sets up and solves the normal equations for S_{mn} from one- or two-dimensional observations, or a combination of both. In the one-dimensional case only the along-scan angle (η) is used; this applies to data from the main astrometric field. In the two-dimensional case both η and ζ are used, although in general with different standard errors; this applies to the skymapper data. Although the full attitude can in principle be derived from η alone, the conditioning (and sensitivity to systematic errors) improves drastically if also ζ data are included, even at a much lower accuracy.

One important detail should be added concerning the determination of S_{mn} . The quaternion has four components, but only three degrees of freedom (because $|\mathbf{q}| = 1$); consequently, the normal equations matrix (of size $4N$) constructed as outlined above is in principle singular (of rank $3N$). In practice it may be ‘saved’ by rounding errors, but the resulting updates ΔS_{mn} could become quite large, while leaving \mathbf{q} , after normalization, almost unchanged. Ideally this degeneracy should be removed by adding one constraint of the form $|\mathbf{s}| = 1$ for each degree of freedom. In practice I have found that the degeneracy is more easily eliminated by adding N ‘soft constraints’ in the form of observation equations $\mathbf{S}'_n \Delta \mathbf{S}_n = 0$, where \mathbf{S}_n is the 4-vector $[S_{1n} S_{2n} S_{3n} S_{4n}]'$. These constraints mean that the vectors \mathbf{S}_n do not change their lengths (much) in the updating. The extra observation equations are given a weight (W) which should be chosen with some consideration. Let $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \lambda_{3N} > 0 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0$ be the eigenvalues of the unconstrained normal equations matrix. The soft constraints adds N eigenvalues of size W . Therefore, the condition number of the matrix is minimal as long as $\lambda_1 \geq W \geq \lambda_{3N}$. For numerical stability the weight should be chosen in this range. On the other hand, the standard errors computed

from the diagonal elements of the inverse matrix are correct only for a ‘hard constraint’ corresponding to the limit $W \rightarrow \infty$, which is computationally unfeasible. Thus, a reasonable compromise is $W \sim \lambda_1$, the largest eigenvalue of the unconstrained normal equations matrix. In `attupd` this value is estimated by means of a few eigenvector iterations and the corresponding soft constraints are added before solving the normal equations.

5.7 Calibration updating

The geometric calibration in the along-scan direction, including chromaticity, is simply a (robust) linear regression of the calculated η from Eq. (11) against $C_i - C_0$, which gives η_k as the intercept and Γ_k as the slope. (Alternatively, if chromaticity is not included, η_k is just obtained as the robust weighted mean of the calculated values.)

The geometric calibration across scan, $\Delta\zeta_k$, is obtained as the robust weighted mean of the differences $\zeta_l^{(\text{calc})} - \tilde{\zeta}_l$.

The photometric zero point, μ_k , is obtained as the robust weighted mean of the differences $m_{i(l)} - \tilde{m}_l$, where m_i is the current magnitude estimate of the source (real magnitude, not instrument magnitude).

5.8 Updating of global parameters

In the global processing, the residuals in instrument angles are analysed with respect to the global parameter vector \mathbf{g} (here only containing one element, γ):

$$\begin{bmatrix} (\eta^{(\text{obs})} - \eta^{(\text{calc})}) \cos \zeta^{(\text{calc})} \\ \zeta^{(\text{obs})} - \zeta^{(\text{calc})} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{g}'} \Delta \mathbf{g} + \text{noise}. \quad (17)$$

The partial derivative $\partial \mathbf{f} / \partial \mathbf{g}'$ is returned by `dir_f`. The processing is a trivial application of iterative least-squares with weight reduction from `whuber` (Sect. 5.1).

Appendix: Fortran routines

This Appendix gives (in alphabetical order) the header comments for the Fortran routines mentioned in this document. The complete Fortran code, including dependencies, is available in separate files. All routines have been tested in dedicated simulations.

Attitude updating: attupd

```
c*****
c      SUBROUTINE attupd(n, tau, bsc0, mode, glb, apar, tobs, fobs, ferr,
c      +                wa, wb, wc, wd,      bsc, ierr, wr)
c*****
c
c  Attitude updating: accumulates and solves normal equations for
c  the B-spline representation of the attitude in a given time interval
c
c  INPUT:
c  n          = number of degrees of freedom of the spline (>= 4)
c  tau(-1:n+2) = knot sequence
c  bsc0(1:4,1:n) = array of B-spline coeff. for the current attitude
c  mode       = integer (0,1,2,3) specifying what will be done:
c              <= 0 : initialisation of work arrays (tobs, fobs, ferr
c                  are not used)
c              = 1 : normals will be accumulated for along-scan angle
c                  only (tobs, fobs(1) and ferr(1) are used)
c              = 2 : normals will be accumulated for along- and across-
c                  scan angles (tobs, fobs(1:2), ferr(1:2) are used)
c              >= 3 : no more observations; the normal equations are
c                  solved (tobs, fobs and ferr are not used)
c  glb(1)     = global parameter
c  apar(1:6)  = astrometric parameters of the source
c  tobs       = time of observation
c  fobs(1:2)  = observed instrument angles (eta,zeta)
c  ferr(1:2)  = standard errors of the obs. (sigma_eta,sigma_zeta)
c  wa(*)      = work array of size >= 64*n
c  wb(*)      = work array of size >= 4*n
c  wc(*)      = work array of size >= 4*n
c  wd(*)      = work array of size >= 4*n
c
c  OUTPUT:
c  bsc(1:4,1:n) = array of B-spline coeff. for the fitted attitude;
c               returned only in mode = 3
c  ierr         = 0 on normal return
c               < 0 if tobs not in [tau(2),tau(n-1)] (for mode = 1 or 2)
c               > 0 if least-squares equations are singular (this
c               usually means that there are too few observations);
c               this could only happen in mode = 3
c  wr(1:2)     = average weight reduction along-scan (wr(1)) and
c               across-scan (wr(2)). Returned only for mode = 3
c               (in mode = 1 or 2 they return the applied w.r. on
c               the current observation)
c
c  This routine should be used as follows (NOTE - in between calls,
c  the work arrays wa and wb must not be changed! They are used to
c  store the normal equations!):
c
c  1. first call it with mode = 0 to initialize the work arrays
c
c  2. then for each observation value (eta) or pair (eta,zeta), call
c     it with mode = 1 or 2, respectively
c
c  3. finally make a call with mode = 3 to get the updated attitude.
c
```

```

c 4. elements of the covariance matrix can be obtained from wa by
c means of bpbsl. For instance, to get the standard error of
c bsc(k,m), do the following:
c----
c   j = 4*(m-1) + k
c   DO i = 1, 4*n
c       wc(i) = 0d0
c   ENDDO
c   wc(j) = 1d0
c   CALL dpbsl(wa, 16, 4*n, 15, wc)
c   sigma(k,m) = dsqrt(wc(j))
c----
c   wc is now the jth column (or row) of the covariance matrix.
c
c NOTE: the unit of standard errors is defined by the parameter
c unit_se in 'const_math.h'.

```

Satellite ephemeris: bary_sat

```

c*****
c      SUBROUTINE bary_sat(t, b, vb, h)
c*****
c
c Calculates the approximate barycentric and heliocentric ephemerides
c of a satellite in the Sun-Earth L2 position.
c
c INPUT:
c t      = time in days from J2000.0 (= JD 2451545.0)
c
c OUTPUT:
c b(1:3) = rectangular barycentric coordinates of the satellite
c         in the equatorial frame (ICRS), in [AU]
c vb(1:3) = barycentric coordinate velocity of the satellite
c         in [AU/day]
c h(1:3) = rectangular heliocentric coordinates of the satellite
c         in the equatorial frame (ICRS), in [AU]
c
c METHOD:
c The heliocentric satellite position vector is computed as rsat=1.01
c times the approximate position of the Earth-Moon barycentre. The
c barycentric vector is obtained by adding the sun's barycentric
c position from bary_sun. Maximum errors are about 3e-4 AU in b and h,
c and 2e-6 AU/day in bv (valid for the period 2000-2020).
c
c Note: the heliocentric velocity vh(1:3), although calculated, is
c not returned
c
c LL, Lund Observatory, 2001 Feb 22

```

Calculate B-splines: bspl

```

c*****
c      SUBROUTINE bspl(tau, x, left, b0, b1)
c*****
c
c Subroutine bspl returns the values and first derivatives of the four
c non-zero cubic B-splines in the interval tau(left) <= x < tau(left+1)
c
c INPUT:
c tau(*) = knot sequence
c x      = point at which the B-splines should be evaluated
c left   = integer chosen (usually) such that

```

```

c          tau(left) <= x < tau(left+1)
c          (left can be found by subroutine findleft)
c
c  OUTPUT:
c  b0(1:4) = values of the cubic B-splines at point x
c  b1(1:4) = first derivatives (wrt x) of the B-splines at point x
c
c  Based on the subroutine BSPLVB in C. de Boor, A Practical Guide to
c  Splines, Springer 1978
c
c  Calculation of derivatives was added (perhaps inefficiently) as
c  the analytical derivative of each statement in the original BSPLVB
c  routine, using that (d/dx)deltar(j) = -1 and (d/dx)deltal(j) = +1.
c
c  The order of the spline is set by the parameter KORD (=4 for cubic)
c
c  LL, Lund Observatory, 2001 Feb 25

```

Calculate instrument angles: dir_f

```

c*****
c          SUBROUTINE dir_f(uprp, duda, dudg, q,      f, dfda, dfdg, dfdq)
c*****
c
c  For given proper direction (+ derivatives) and attitude quaternion,
c  calculate the field coordinates f = (eta,zeta) and derivatives
c
c  INPUT:
c  uprp(1:3)      = proper direction to the star at time t
c  duda(1:3,1:6) = partial derivatives of uprp(1:3) wrt apar(1:6) *)
c  dudg(1:3,1)   = partial derivatives of uprp(1:3) wrt glb(1)
c  q(1:4)        = attitude quaternion
c
c  OUTPUT:
c  f(1:2)        = field angles f(1) = eta, f(2) = zeta
c  dfda(1:2,1:6) = partial derivatives of f(1:2) wrt apar(1:6) *)
c  dfdg(1:2,1)   = partial derivatives of f(1:2) wrt glb(1)
c  dfdq(1:2,1:4) = partial derivatives of f(1:2) wrt q(1:4)
c
c  *) NOTE: cos-factor implicit in first angle of apar() and f()
c
c  LL, Lund Observatory, 2001 Feb 22

```

Calculate proper direction: dir_prp

```

c*****
c          SUBROUTINE dir_prp(glb, apar, t,      uprp, duda, dudg)
c*****
c
c  For given time and stellar parameters, calculate
c  proper direction and derivatives wrt the parameters
c
c  INPUT:
c  glb(1) = PPN parameter gamma (in GR light deflection formula)
c  apar(1) = right ascension at epoch ep0 [rad]
c  apar(2) = declination at epoch ep0 [rad]
c  apar(3) = parallax at epoch ep0 [rad]
c  apar(4) = proper motion in right ascension at epoch ep0 [rad/day]
c  apar(5) = proper motion in declination at epoch ep0 [rad/day]
c  apar(6) = "sixth parameter" (radial velocity times parallax)
c           at epoch ep0 [rad/day]
c  t      = time of observation [days from J2000]

```

```

c
c OUTPUT:
c uprp(1:3) = proper direction to the star at time t
c duda(1:3,1:6) = partial derivatives of uprp(1:3) wrt apar(1:6) *)
c dudg(1:3,1) = partial derivatives of uprp(1:3) wrt gbl(1)
c
c *) NOTE: duda(1:3,1) are the part. deriv. wrt apar(1)*cos(apar(2))
c
c LL, Lund Observatory, 2001 Feb 22

```

Quaternion interpolation: qint

```

c*****
SUBROUTINE qint(n, tau, s, t, q0, q1, ierr)
c*****
c
c Interpolate attitude data to give quaternion q0 and derivative
c q1 = d(q0)/dt for the specified time t0.
c
c INPUT:
c n = number of degrees of freedom of the spline
c tau(-1:n+2) = knot sequence with tau(2) = tbeg, tau(n-1) = tend
c s(1:4,1:n) = B-spline coefficients
c t = time for which q0 and q1 are wanted
c
c OUTPUT:
c q0(1:4) = quaternion defining the attitude at time t
c q1(1:4) = time derivative of q0 at time t
c ierr = 0 on normal return
c > 0 if t is not in [tbeg,tend]
c
c LL, Lund Observatory, 2001 Feb 22

```

Robust weighted mean: robwm

```

c*****
SUBROUTINE robwm(n, x, s, xave, se_xave)
c*****
c
c Calculates the robust weighted mean of x(1:n), given the standard
c errors s(1:n) (which must be > 0). The standard error of the mean
c is also calculated.
c
c INPUT:
c n = number of values
c x(i) = array of values, i = 1 to n
c s(i) = array of standard errors, i = 1, n
c
c OUTPUT:
c xave = weighted mean of x(1) through x(n)
c se_xave = standard error of the weighted mean
c
c METHOD:
c The initial statistical weight of x(i) is s(i)**(-2). Depending on
c the size of the normalized residual z = (x(i)-xave)/s(i), the weight
c is iteratively reduced according to whuber(z). After convergence,
c se_xave is obtained from the sum of the reduced weights.
c
c SUBPROGRAMS CALLED:
c d.p. function whuber(z)
c
c L Lindegren, Lund Observatory (2001)

```

Cubic spline fit by least-squares: splfit

```
C*****
      SUBROUTINE splfit(n, tau, mul, nob, t, q, wa, wb, bsc, ierr)
C*****
c
c Given a knot sequence and a set of data points (t, q), fit
c a cubic spline by least-squares to the data points and return
c the B-spline coefficients. The routine allows to handle mul
c different data sets in parallel, with same t-values.
c
c INPUT:
c n          = number of degrees of freedom of the spline (>= 4)
c tau(-1:n+2) = knot sequence
c mul        = number of data sets treated in parallel
c nob        = number of data points per data set
c t(1:nob)   = abscissae for the data points in every set
c q(1:mul,1:nob) = ordinates for the different data sets
c wa(*)      = work array of size >= 4*n
c wb(*)      = work array of size >= n
c
c OUTPUT:
c bsc(1:mul,1:n) = array of B-spline coeff. for the mul data sets
c ierr          = 0 on normal return
c                > 0 if least-squares equations are singular (this
c                usually means that there are too few data points)
c
c L Lindegren, Lund Observatory, 2001 March 16
```

Define knot sequence for spline: taudef

```
C*****
      SUBROUTINE taudef(tbeg, tend, dtmax, nmax, n, tau, ierr)
C*****
c
c Set up an equidistant knot sequence for a given cubic spline
c interval [tbeg,tend] and maximum knot interval dtmax.
c
c INPUT:
c tbeg      = abscissa (time) for the beginning of spline interval
c tend      = abscissa (time) for the end of spline interval
c dtmax     = maximum separation between the interior knots
c naxm      = upper limit to the dimension of tau
c
c OUTPUT:
c n         = the number of degrees of freedom of the spline. On
c            return, the spline interval is divided into n-3 equal
c            knot intervals.
c tau(-1:n+2) = the knot sequence
c ierr      = 0 on normal return
c            > 0 on error (n+2 > nmax)
c
c NOTE: in the calling programme, tau must be dimensioned to
c tau(-1:NMAX), where NMAX is at least as great as the argument nmax.
c
c LL, Lund Observatory, 2001 March 13
```